

A Study of Dialectical Method in Socrates' the Concept of Good and Evil

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Abstract

Dialectical Method is a method of seeking and arriving at the truth. Dialectical method in philosophy of Socrates is to reconcile the two extremes or to deny one opposite and to accept another opposite that which can be found in the dialogues of Socrates. The aim of dialectical method in Socrates philosophy is to know the objective knowledge of concepts. Socrates arrive at the different conclusions such as reality or ultimate truth and concept and relative truth.

Introduction

The Dialectical Method

Dialectical Method is a method of seeking and arriving at the truth. There will be many ways in seeking and arriving at the truth. In fact, the word 'dialectic' comes from the word 'dialogue'. Di means two or double. Dialogue means that discussion between people with different opinions to understand the terms clearly and distinctly. Dialectic originates from the Greek expression of the art of conversation. It has great variety of meanings and has anything in common. Generally it can be described that dialectical method is a method of seeking and sometimes arriving at the truth by using three ways (1) avoiding the two extremes, (2) reconciling the two extremes, and (3) denying one opposite and accepting another opposite. In the process of dialectical method there are some steps. In this paper some of these processes will be mentioned in the respective chapters.

Paul Edwards in his "Encyclopedia of Philosophy" describes the meaning of the terms as follows;

"among the more important meanings of the term have been (1) the method of refutation by examining logical consequences, (2) Sophistical reasoning, (3) the method of division or repeated logical analysis of genera into species (4) an investigation of the supremely general abstract notions by some process of reasoning leading up to them from particular case or hypothesis, (5) logical reasoning or debate using premises that are merely probable or generally accepted (6) formal logic (7) the criticism of the logic of illusion, showing the contradictions into which reason falls in trying to go beyond experience to deal with transcendental objects, and (8) the logical development of thought or reality through thesis and antithesis to a synthesis of these opposites."

Perhaps, dialectical method may be started in the fifth century B.C since Zeno introduced his famous paradoxes. First the Philosophers seem to use the term as indirect logical arguments to defeat an opponent Zeno for serious philosophical purposes. But in the hands of sophists, it became a mere instrument for winning a dispute. Protagoras, one of the sophists claimed that he could make the worse argument appear the better. Thus, in the hands of the sophists the aim of the dialectical method leads to rhetoric than to logic or philosophy.

Unlike Sophists, Socrates preferred to seek the truth. He did not aim to win the argument. The major element in Socrates' dialectic is a prolonged cross-examination refuting the opponent's original thesis by getting him to draw from it. He used a series of questions and

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answers by drawing a consequence that contradicts it. So Socratic Dialectic is a refined form of Zennoian paradoxes and thus Socrates stands in contrast to sophists. For Socrates, dialectic seems to have been literally the art of discussion a search for truth by question and answers.

With Plato the notion of dialectic is developed. Dialectic is regarded there as the supreme philosophical method, and it is indeed the highest of human arts. Plato had described the dialectician as the man who knows how to ask and answer questions. The view of dialectic as question and answer is also the Socratic element and it forms as the single thread that runs through out the conversation process when trying to find out the definition of the concepts. For Socrates, dialectic seeks the unchanging essence of each thing. So it always had the same subject matter. But in Plato's dialogues the kind of dialectical reasoning seems to change. In some dialogues it was some kind of operation on hypothesis whereas in another dialogues there is an emphasis on division as a method. Division consists of a repeated analysis of genera into species of the more general notions into less general ones, as a way of arriving at a definition when no further division is possible. This process is complemented by the opposite process of synthesis or collection.

Socrates used to discuss the popular and hastily formed opinions of his company. He tests by means of illustrations taken from everyday life showing that they are not well-founded so that modification and correction are needed. He helps those who are taking part in the dialogues to form the correct opinion, by suggesting relevant instances. He does not content until the truth has develop step by step. The essential features of the Socratic Method can be found in the Euthydemus. By skillful questioning, Socrates gets a young man, Euthydemus to confess his ambition to become a great politician and statesman. Then Socrates suggests that in order to pursue his ambition, he must hope to become a just man himself.

In this way, Socrates' definitions are evolved by a process of induction. By generalization the examples of a just man Socrates formed a definition a just man. The aim is to discover the essential characteristics of the subjects to be defined, to reach clear and distinct notion or concepts. At times Socrates tests the statements made by going back to first principles, by criticizing statements in the light of basic definition which is assumed to be correct. This is deductive method. For example, when we say that this man is a better citizen than that one, we must give reasons for it by referring to an acceptable definition of a good citizen.

Knowledge is concerned with the general and typical, not with the particular and accidental. According to Socrates, knowledge is possible only if we pursue the proper method. Socrates put the method into practice. He applies his method to all human problems, particularly to the problems of morality and seeks to find a rational basis for conduct. Socrates endeavors to understand the meaning of morality to discover a rational principle of the right and wrong, a criterion by which to decide moral issues. Socrates says that knowledge is the highest good. "Knowledge is virtue" is the central thesis of Socrates' ethics. According to him, right thinking is essential to right conduct. If a man does not know what virtue is, if he does not know the meaning of self-control, courage and justice and piety and their opposites, he cannot be virtuous. But if a man knows what virtue is, he will be virtuous. So knowledge is both necessary and sufficient condition of virtue. Without knowledge virtue is impossible.

Socrates was stimulated by the Sophists. But he was not willing to agree with them. He was most interested in how to live a good life. Thus his dialectic was dealt with the meaning of right and wrong. Socrates believes that there must be a basic principle of right and wrong. There must have a measure which would apply beyond anyone's belief or opinion. Thus in Plato's dialogues he asks questions "What is the good?" "What is the highest good by which all else in the universe is measured?" According to Socrates, no man is voluntarily bad. If one

know what is right then he will do it. When one knows that a thing is good, then he will choose to do that thing. So the most important thing is to discover what is good. According to him, a man's life is an always inquiring life trying to discover what is good. It is the best kind of life, the only worth living. In order to achieve this life he tries to find things which are good by using his dialectic method.

The objective which Socrates set himself was not to construct a system of philosophy, but to arouse in men the love of truth and virtue, to help them to think right in order that they might live right. Socrates proposed the moral doctrine that no man does wrong voluntarily. He bases his thought on the ground that everyone seeks happiness and seeks what he thinks to be his own good. If every man seeks happiness by achieving the good, wrongdoing will come through ignorance. This is the morality of the wise man because he has knowledge of the good. The morality of the wise man is not the only moral theory known to man. The morality of a saint is based upon love and the spirit of Sacrifice. Again, the hero has courage, and nothing requires him to be a wise man. In the same way the prophet is not a wise man. He is inspired. Researcher will use some of the Plato's dialogues in order to explain the Socratic dialectic because the Socratic Philosophy relies almost exclusively on the Plato's dialogues.

The dialectical method in Socrates' philosophy will be studied. The method of reconciling the two extremes and the method of denying one opposite and accepting another opposite will be dialectical methods in Socrates' Philosophy. A Philosophical method of conceptual analysis is dialectical method of Socrates. In this chapter researcher will study dialogue on the concept of knowledge, virtue and good and evil (relative truth).

Dialectical Method on the Concept of Good and Evil

In this dialogue Protagoras defined the concept of good and evil. The Protagoras is made between Socrates and the great sophist, Protagoras. The dialogue started with a request made by Hippocrates that Socrates would introduce him to Protagoras. Socrates advises him to find out 'what Protagoras will make him into', before he becomes his pupils.

When they reach before Protagoras, Socrates explains the purpose of their visit to him asking what he will make of Hippocrates. Protagoras answers that he will make him a better and a wise man. Socrates asks in what he will be better. Socrates desires to have a more precise answer. Protagoras replies that he will teach him prudence in private and public affairs. That is he will teach him the science or knowledge of human life.

Socrates admits that this is a noble profession but he is or rather would be doubtful, whether such knowledge can be taught if Protagoras had not assured him of the fact, for two reasons: (1) Because the Athenian people, who recognized in their assemblies the distinction between the skilled and the unskilled in the arts, do not distinguish between the trained politician and the untrained: (2) Because the wisest and best Athenian citizens do not teach their sons political virtue. This is the objection made by Socrates.

Protagoras explains his views in the following way. These are not, like the arts, to be given to a few only, but all men are to be taken part. Therefore the Athenian people are right in distinguishing between the skilled and unskilled in the arts, and not between skilled and unskilled politicians. For all men have the political virtues to a certain degree. The political virtues can be taught and acquired, in the opinion of the Athenians. It is proved by the fact that they punish evil-doers with a view to prevention. Virtues is not the private possession of any man but is shared by all. However it depends on which each individual is by nature capable. Even the worst of civilized mankind will appear virtuous and just if we compare them with savages.

Socrates is wrong in supposing that there are not teachers of virtues because all men are teachers in a degree. Like Protagoras, some are better than others, and with this result we ought to be satisfied. Socrates is very much satisfied with the explanation of Protagoras although he has still a doubt in his mind. He asks Protagoras that he has spoken of the virtues. Are they many or one? Are they parts of whole or different names of the same thing? Protagoras replies that they are parts, like the parts of a face, which have their several functions and no one part is like any other part.

This is cross-examined by Socrates. "Is justice just and is holiness holy? And are justice and holiness opposed to one another?" "Then justice is unholy", Protagoras would rather say that justice is different from holiness, but from a certain point of view it is nearly the same. However, he has to admit that everything has but one opposite. For example folly is opposed to wisdom; and folly is also opposed to temperance; and therefore temperance and wisdom are the same.

Protagoras is aware that he will soon be compelled by the dialectics of Socrates to admit that the temperate is the just. Therefore he defends himself with his favorite weapon. He makes a long speech not much to the point which is not accepted by Socrates. Socrates must beg Protagoras to speak shorter. As Protagoras refers he rises to depart. But Callias says that it is who thinks him unreasonable in not allowing Protagoras the liberty of speaking he likes. For Socrates admits his inability to speak long; just as Protagoras is unable to speak short.

Protagoras refers to a poem of Simonides of Ceos, where he could find a contradiction. In the poem the poet says, 'Hardly can a man become truly good'. Then he reproached Pittacus for having said, 'Hardly can a man be good'. How is this to be reconciled? Socrates draws a distinction between to be and to become. To be good is difficult whereas to become good is easy. Then the word difficult or hard is explained to mean 'evil' by Simonides and his country men the Ceans. Socrates gives another and more elaborate explanation of the whole passage but the old question is repeated, 'Whether the virtues are one or many?' Protagoras replies that four out of the five virtues are in some degree similar but fifth, courage is unlike the rest because many men are utterly, unrighteous, unholy, intemperate and ignorant but they are remarkable for their courage. Socrates stops him by asking whether Protagoras means the brave men are the confident and the confident are those who know their business or profession. Then Socrates says that the divers are confident because they have Knowledge. So courage is knowledge.

Socrates continues by saying that he would like to know whether pleasure is not the only good and pain the only evil. Protagoras says that 'some pleasures are good, some pains are evil'. It is what mankind generally accepted. Then Socrates asks Protagoras. What the latter thinks of knowledge and whether he agree with common opinion that knowledge is overcome by passion or whether he holds that knowledge is power. Protagoras agrees that knowledge is overcome by passion or whether he holds that knowledge is power. Protagoras agrees that knowledge is certainly a governing power.

However, there are many who know what is best but act contrary because they are influenced by pleasure. But this opposite of good and evil is really the opposite of a greater or lesser amount of pleasure. Pleasures are evils because they end in pain and pains are goods because they end in pleasure. Pleasure is seen to be the only good. The only evil is where we prefer the lesser pleasure to be the greater.

Socrates concludes that knowledge is the governing principle of human life. Ignorance is the origin of all evil because no one prefers the less pleasure to the greater or the greater pain to the less, except from ignorance. Hippias and Prodicus, as well as Protagoras, admit that the conclusion drawn by Socrates is sound. Then Socrates discusses the case of courage. He says

that no one will choose the evil or will refuse the good unless he is ignorant. This is why the reason cowards refuse to go against dangers because they are ignorant of good, and honour and pleasure. Then why are the brave men willing to go against dangers? They are ready to go against dangers because they have the right knowledge about what are and what are not dangers. Then courage is knowledge and cowardice is ignorance.

Protagoras remains silent and after that he tells Socrates to finish his argument by himself. That is Protagoras applauds Socrates' earnestness and this style of discussion. This is the dialectical method of logical reasoning and the logical development of thought or reality through thesis and antithesis to a synthesis of those opposites.

Evaluation

Dialectical Method is a method of seeking and arriving at the truth. The objective of dialectical method in Socrates philosophy is to know knowledge of concepts. Without the dialectical method in Socrates we would be ignorant of some concepts.

In Western philosophy we are generally told of two sources of knowledge, perception and inference. In the dialectical method in Socrates philosophy only reasoning is regarded as sources of knowledge. In fact, Socrates invented a dialectical method of conceptual analysis. It is conceptual or definitional. It sets as the goal of knowledge of concepts such as concept of knowledge, virtue, good and evil, soul and so on.

Socrates endeavors to understand the meaning of a rational principle of right and wrong. This attempt led him to the conclusion that knowledge is virtue. Thus we can say that the teaching of Socrates is essentially ethical in character. The ethical teaching of Socrates was founded upon a theory of knowledge. He believed that search of knowledge is of most important. For him, right thinking is essential to right action. It is meant that in order to steer a ship or a rule a state, a man must have knowledge of the construction and the function of the ship, or of nature of and purpose of state. Similarly, unless a man knows what virtue is unless he knows the meaning of love, temperance, friendship, courage and their opposites, he cannot be virtuous. But, knowing what virtue is, he will be virtuous. Socrates said that no man is voluntarily bad or voluntarily good.

In conclusion, dialectical method is a method of seeking and arriving at the truth so can say that dialectical method in Socrates arrives at concept or relative truth. The chief aim of Socrates was to order into the intellectual and moral chaos of the sophistry which threatened the foundations of morality and the state. Thus this aim was not to construct a philosophical system but to arouse men to love the truth and virtue.

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